

Rate-Distortion/Complexity Analysis of HEVC, VVC and AV1 Video Codecs

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Abstract With the advent of smartphones and tablets, the amount of on-line video traffic has increased enormously. This, together with the growing popularity of high-definition video, motivated the development of the High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) standard, released in 2013, with the aim of achieving a 50% bitrate reduction with respect to its predecessor, namely H.264/MPEG-4 Advanced Video Coding (AVC). However, new contents with greater resolutions and requirements arise every day, making it necessary to reduce the bitrate to a further extent. In this regard, the efforts to become the leading video codec in the market resulted in two main contenders: the Joint Video Experts Team (JVET), which leads the development of the Versatile Video Coding (VVC) standard, and the Alliance for Open Media (AOMedia), which spearheads the AOMedia Video 1 (AV1) project. In this context, this paper presents a rate-distortion/complexity analysis of HEVC, VVC and AV1 main video codecs using objective measures of assessment in order to analyze their real capabilities. The analysis, which was done using well-defined test conditions, reveals that VVC considerably outperforms both HEVC and AV1 in terms of coding efficiency.

Keywords HEVC · VVC · AV1 · Computational Time · Coding Efficiency

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1 Introduction

Over the last decades, the market for standardized video codecs has been dominated by the standardization groups ISO/IEC Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) and ITU-T Video Coding Experts Group (VCEG): H.261 (1991), MPEG-1 (1993), MPEG-2 (1994), H.263 (1995), MPEG-4 (1998) and H.264/MPEG-4 Advanced Video Coding (AVC) (2003) [1]. From 2010, the two organizations merged their efforts into the so-called Joint Collaborative Team on Video Coding (JCT-VC), which resulted in the release of the High Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) standard in 2013. This new video coding standard was released as MPEG-H Part 2 by ISO/IEC, and as H.265 by ITU-T [2].

HEVC was developed to replace the H.264/MPEG-4 AVC standard, which had dominated digital video services in all segments of the domestic and professional markets for over ten years, and to support resolutions such as full high definition (FHD) (1920×1080), and 4K (3840×2160). In terms of rate-distortion (R-D) performance, HEVC roughly doubles the compression performance of the H.264/MPEG-4 AVC standard, but at the cost of extremely high computational and storage complexities during encoding [3]. In addition to these capabilities, the latest version of HEVC, which was released in 2019, also provides support for multiview, scalable and 3D video applications.

The consumption of multimedia content, however, has not stopped growing since the development of HEVC. The increasing consumption of more immersive video formats and higher resolution has pressured the industry and scientific community into innovating in even more efficient video compression techniques. Typically, such video formats also come along with significantly higher raw data rates such that any streaming or broadcasting service for this kind of video formats cannot be economically performed without the corresponding leap in coding efficiency performance. In fact, the cost for distributing video content is a major factor on the bottom line for most large infrastructure and video service providers regardless of the distribution channel.

With this in mind, the international organizations ITU-T and ISO/IEC have jointly created a new collaboration framework under the name of Joint Video Experts Team (JVET) to analyze the potential need for standardization of future video coding technologies with a compression capability that significantly surpasses the one achieved by HEVC, especially for streaming ultra high definition (UHD), panorama video content from sport events, concerts, shows, 360-degree immersive multimedia and high-dynamic-range (HDR) video content. The new video coding standard in development, named Versatile Video Coding (VVC), has integrated the most promising future technologies into the so-called VVC Test Model (VTM) [4]. In this regard, VTM is currently the experimental software of the JVET, and contains coding tools that have been designed to achieve a coding performance superior to that of HEVC. The official standardization activities for the VVC video coding standard started in April 2018 after evaluating the submissions to the corresponding call for proposals (CfP) for future video coding technologies [5]. The next video coding standard is currently targeted to be finalized by the end of 2020.

However, HEVC has not taken off the same way as prior standards did. The joint patent holders of the technology have demanded license fees that many companies consider either too high or too difficult to justify. In particular, HEVC adoption has been low in the streaming scenario, and it is the reason why some of the largest companies such as Amazon, Netflix, Google, Intel, Cisco, Microsoft, Nvidia, and AMD, among others, formed the Alliance for Open Media (AOMedia), a joint development foundation with the aim to create the AOMedia Video 1 (AV1) codec as a royalty-free video coding format [6, 7]. The main goal of its development is to achieve substantial compression gain over state-of-the-art codecs while maintaining practical decoding complexity and hardware feasibility.

The industry-driven development of AV1 has used the proprietary VP9 video coding scheme as its starting point [8]. By contrast, the VTM software, as an experimental platform for evaluating future video coding technologies, has been partially built upon the HEVC Test Model (HM) reference implementation of the HEVC standard [9]. Although the two developments have different driving forces, both share a common goal: the improvement of the compression efficiency relative to existing video coding schemes. In this light, the question on the relative performance of both alternatives in terms of compression efficiency has already been analyzed in terms of both objective quality [10–14] and subjective quality [15]. In this regard, while the performance of HM has been stable since the specification of the HEVC bitstream syntax, and thus its coding tools, the current performance of AV1 and VTM only represents a snapshot of their development. The main conclusion of the aforementioned works shows that the different versions of the VTM and AV1 implementations have great impact on their coding efficiency and computational cost.

This paper focuses on a comprehensive performance evaluation of these two lines of development for the next leading video coding schemes, namely the AV1 project and the VVC standard, through the analysis of their most representative video codecs, i.e. AV1 and VTM, respectively. A large test set of video sequences with different types of content, multiple resolutions, and various frame rates has been used as the common baseline. For each sequence and test candidate, four different rate points associated with varying qualities of reconstruction have been generated. Therefore, the main contribution of this paper is the establishment of a common framework of evaluation of the two codecs, VVC and AV1, and the subsequent analysis of the results achieved by their reference encoders in terms of coding efficiency and encoder run time. This enables the objective assessment of the performance achieved by the two candidates in a wide spectrum of use cases, showing their benefits and limitations, and their feasibility in current scenarios.

When comparing the two contending coding schemes against HM in terms of Bjøntegaard delta rate (BD-rate), the analysis reveals that VTM achieves an average BD-rate of -23.22%, while AV1 results in a BD-rate increase of 41.15%, thus lower coding efficiency than the baseline [16, 17]. As far as the encoding time is concerned, VTM and AV1 involve a $4.45\times$ and $1.28\times$ increase, respectively. Therefore, it is evinced from the analysis that the AV1 encoder

Fig. 1 Block diagram of a typical hybrid video encoder.

is not able to outperform the coding efficiency of HM despite the increase in encoding time. This reflects the fact that VVC is currently leading the future of video compression, albeit at the expense of requiring significantly larger computational efforts.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly introduces the distinguishing features of VVC and AV1 compared to HEVC. Section 3 presents the evaluation setup used in order to compare the video codecs. The rate-distortion/complexity analysis between the video codecs under study is given in Sect. 4. Finally, Sect. 5 concludes the paper.

2 Technical Background

While the developments of VVC and AV1 have followed different paths, the two codecs share many similarities in their basic encoding and decoding flowcharts. In this regard, both follow the same hybrid video coding scheme established by their predecessors, including HEVC. Such scheme is shown in Fig. 1, where blocks shaded in gray represent decoding modules. Therefore, it is the different

coding tools adopted by each of the two technologies what makes a difference in their capabilities and coding efficiency. The following subsections will highlight the main tools introduced in VVC and AV1.

2.1 Versatile Video Coding (VVC)

As mentioned above, VVC is the new video coding standard project of the JVET, which builds upon HEVC and introduces video coding technologies with superior compression capabilities. The main features of VVC shown in this section will be described as per its second working draft, which corresponds to the version of VTM used in the analysis [4].

In HEVC, the image partitioning is defined by coding tree units (CTUs), with a maximum size of 64×64 pixels, that are split into coding units (CUs) by using a quadtree structure to adapt to various local characteristics. The decision of whether to code a picture area using inter-picture (temporal) or intra-picture (spatial) prediction is made at the CU level. Each CU can contain one or more prediction units (PUs), according to the PU splitting type, and transform units (TUs), according to another quadtree structure similar to the CTU. In VVC, the concept of multiple partition types, including CU, PU and TU, is no longer needed with the incorporation of the multi-type tree (MTT) structure for blocks, using binary and ternary split segmentations. This provides more flexibility for CU partition shapes to better match the local characteristics of the video sequence.

In the MTT structure, CTUs have a maximum size of 128×128 pixels. Each CTU is first partitioned by a quadtree structure into square CUs. Then, leaf nodes can be further partitioned by a binary/ternary tree structure. By the use of this tree, each CU can be split into horizontal and vertical CUs. In VVC, the size of the CU may be as large as the CTU or as small as 4×4 samples. For the case of the 4:2:0 chroma format, the maximum chroma size is 64×64 and the minimum chroma size is 2×2 . Regarding the boundaries of a frame, when a portion of a tree node block exceeds the bottom or right picture boundary, the tree node block is forced to be split until all samples of every coded CU are located inside the picture boundaries.

In addition, there are some restrictions on redundant CU splits. For example, two levels of consecutive binary splits in one direction could have the same coding block structure as a ternary tree split followed by a binary tree split of the central partition. In this case, the second alternative would be prohibited.

An example of a CTU structure with its associated MTT in VVC is depicted in Fig. 2. First, the CTU is split into four blocks of equal size by the use of a quadtree, and then the binary/ternary tree begins the horizontal and vertical divisions.

For intra prediction, in order to capture finer edge directions present in natural videos, the directional intra modes are extended from 33, as defined in HEVC, to 65. The Planar and DC modes remain the same. All these modes are depicted in Fig. 3, in which directions in red are the ones introduced in VVC.

Fig. 2 Example of an MTT partitioning in VVC.

Fig. 3 Intra prediction modes in VVC.

These new directional prediction modes are applied for all block sizes, in both luma and chroma components. To accommodate the binary representation in the stream of the number of directional intra modes, an intra mode coding method with 3 most probable modes (MPMs) is carried out in this module, which includes neighbour, derived and default intra modes. Another technique incorporated in the intra module is called the cross-component linear model (CCLM), and is aimed at reducing redundancies between luma and chroma components. The idea is that the chrominance samples can be predicted on the basis of the reconstructed luminance of the same block by a linear model. The last method incorporated in the intra module is named position-dependent intra prediction combination (PDPC), which combines unfiltered and filtered boundary reference samples, and it is applied to certain intra modes.

Concerning inter prediction, VVC includes three new inter prediction coding tools that are different from HEVC:

- Affine motion compensated prediction: in HEVC, a translation motion model is applied for motion compensation. However, there are many kinds of motion in the real world such as rotation, perspective or zoom. For this reason, VVC has been extended to two motion compensation models. The first one uses information from two motion vectors (MVs), while the second one uses up to three vectors. The MV of the center sample of each sub-block is calculated according to these models, using 1/16 fraction ac-

curacy. Then the motion compensation interpolation filters are applied to generate the prediction of each sub-block.

- Subblock-based temporal MV prediction (SbTMVP): similar to temporal MV prediction (TMVP) method in HEVC, SbTMVP uses the motion information of a previously encoded picture. However, SbTMVP differs from TMVP in two aspects. On the one hand, SbTMVP predicts motion at sub-CU level. On the other hand, SbTMVP applies a motion shift before referencing the temporal motion information in the collocated picture. This shift is obtained from the information of neighboring CUs in the current frame.
- Adaptive MV resolution (AMVR): in contrast to HEVC, whose MV differences (MVDs) are signaled in units of quarter-luma-sample, MVDs are coded in units of quarter-luma-sample, integer-luma-sample or four-luma-sample in the AMVR scheme.

In VVC, the highest accuracy of explicitly signaled MVs is quarter-luma-sample. In some inter prediction modes such as the affine mode, MVs are derived at 1/16 accuracy and motion compensated prediction is performed at 1/16 accuracy. In terms of internal motion field storage, all MVs are stored at 1/16 accuracy.

Regarding the modifications to the transform, which allows the encoder to compact the residual information, VVC incorporates some new transform functions. In this regard, VVC includes a multiple transform selection (MTS) method that allows the encoder to choose among a large set of transform functions to encode the intra and inter CU residual information. The available transform matrices for the MTS method are DCT-II, DCT-VIII and DST-VII.

2.2 AOMedia Video 1 (AV1) Codec

AV1 is an emerging open-source and royalty-free video compression format, which is jointly developed by the AOMedia industry consortium. In this subsection, we briefly review the distinguishing features of AV1 [7].

Regarding block partitioning, AV1 relies on an enhanced quadtree partitioning structure. Pictures are partitioned into superblocks with a maximum size of 128×128 . Superblocks can be partitioned into rectangular shaped blocks, or recursively into square blocks down to a minimum of 4×4 pixels. An example partitioning is shown in Fig. 4. The tree-based partitioning is extended by a wedge mode in which a rectangular block can be partitioned by a wedge into non-rectangular parts for which different predictors are used. In this way, the partitioning can be better adapted to object boundaries.

Concerning intra prediction in AV1, the potential of the intra coder is further explored in various ways providing several modes, e.g. a generic directional predictor, a smooth predictor, and an intra-block copy predictor, among others. The generic directional predictor consists of an angular prediction in one of 56 different directions. The smooth predictor, in turn, is conceptually similar to the Planar mode in VVC and HEVC. The intra-block copy predictor

Fig. 4 Example of a quadtree partitioning in AV1.

allows to refer back to previously reconstructed blocks, similarly to how inter coder refers to blocks from previous frames. For that matter, the location of the reference block is specified by using a displacement vector.

The inter prediction in AV1 has access to up to seven reference pictures of which one or two can be chosen per block, providing both bi-directional compound prediction and uni-directional compound prediction. MVs can be predicted at 8×8 block level by dynamic spatial and temporal MV referencing. To that end, AV1 incorporates a MV reference selection scheme to obtain efficient MV references for a given block by searching both spatial and temporal candidates. AV1 also specifies an overlapped block motion compensation (OBMC) to refine the prediction at block boundaries by utilizing neighboring predictors. Moreover, AV1 supports multiple global motion compensation models: a rotation-zoom model, an affine model, and a perspective model. In this regard, warped motion models introduced in AV1 take into consideration two affine prediction modes: global and local warped motion compensation. While the former is meant for handling camera motions, the latter aims to describe varying local motion implicitly using minimal overhead.

Regarding transform coding, AV1 supports multiple transforms: DCT, asymmetric DST (ADST), flipped ADST, and identity. The identity transform is similar to the transform skip mode of VVC, and it is beneficial for screen content coding. AV1 allows luma inter coding blocks to be partitioned into transform units of multiple sizes that can be represented by a recursive partition from 4×4 to 64×64 . For chroma blocks, only the largest possible transform units are allowed. AV1 includes both linear and non-linear quantization matrices for the quantization.

For the in-loop filtering, AV1 allows several filtering tools to be applied successively to a decoded frame. AV1 combines the constrained low-pass filter from the Thor codec with the directional deringing filter from the Daala codec into the combined constrained directional enhancement (CDEF) tool [18, 19]. This filter merging increases the quality of the filtered picture, while at the same time it reduces the overall complexity compared with two separate fil-

tering processes. Additionally, AV1 adds a new frame super-resolution coding mode which is known to offer perceptual advantages at very low bitrates.

The entropy coding in AV1 is based on a symbol-to-symbol adaptive multi-symbol arithmetic coder. Thereby, a multi-symbol alphabet is encoded with up to 15-bit cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) and an alphabet size of up to 16 symbols. With this entropy coder, multiple binary symbols are combined into non-binary symbols. In this way, the efficiency is increased compared to a binary entropy encoder.

2.3 Encoder Settings and Parameters

As mentioned above, VTM and AV1 follow the same hybrid video coding approach. However, they differ in the specific coding tools used to carry out the encoding. To adjust the visual quality and coding efficiency of the resulting video sequence, which have in turn an effect on the total encoding time, both encoders provide configurable parameters that enable the control of such coding tools and the general encoding process.

The two encoders provide default configurations that ensure a good trade-off between coding efficiency and encoding time in a large number of scenarios. While VTM uses only one predefined configuration, AV1 offers up to nine, typically known as presets, which can be set using the optional parameter `--cpu-used` and a value ranging from 0 to 8, where 0 involves a slower, albeit more efficient encoding, and 8 the fastest encoding possible. These presets enable or disable certain coding tools, which results in different trade-offs. By default, AV1 uses preset 1.

Regarding the encoding pattern, VTM provides an all-intra (AI) mode and three fixed hierarchical frame modes, namely random access (RA), low delay B (LB), and low delay P (LP). The former of the three is aimed at scenarios for which instant skip/forwarding to an arbitrary point in the video is required. With this aim, VTM defines fixed-length group of pictures (GOP) of typically 16 frames that, in combination with the `--IntraPeriod` parameter, determine the intra-refresh rate of the resulting sequence. AV1, in turn, establishes a variable encoding pattern for better bit placement. Nevertheless, it is possible to modify the frequency of appearance of golden frames and key frames by setting the parameters `--min-gf-interval` and `--max-gf-interval`, and `--kf-min-dist` and `--kf-max-dist`, respectively. By setting these values to a fixed value, it is possible to achieve a similar behavior to that of VTM.

As far as rate-control algorithms are concerned, the two encoders offer a constant quantization parameter (CQP) scheme, and a variable bitrate (VBR) algorithm. The former is the approach used by default in VTM, and can be configured using the `--QP` parameter. This, along with the delta quantization parameters (QPs) assigned to each frame in a GOP, determines the QP used for the encoding. In AV1, the use of the CQP scheme is specified by the parameter `--end-usage=q`, and a range of QP values by `--min-q` and `--max-q`. In this regard, AV1 automatically chooses the QP for a frame according to its

context and references. VBR, in turn, is the default scheme in AV1. It can be set on VTM using the `--RateControl` and `--TargetBitrate` parameters, and on AV1 using the `--end-usage=vbr` and `--target-bitrate` parameters. Additionally, AV1 performs a two-pass encoding to improve bit placement, which can be disabled for CQP with `--passes=1`.

Finally, both encoders admit different options to specify the formats of the input sequence, such as width, height or frames per second, and the output bitstream, such as chroma subsampling or bit depth. Moreover, some additional parameters have an effect on the encoding to suit specific scenarios. This is the case of the `--tune=psnr` parameter in AV1, which maximizes the peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) metric of the resulting stream. This is useful when comparing AV1 against other encoders.

3 Evaluation Setup

Once the main features of both VVC and AV1 have been described, this section will lay the foundations for the performed rate-distortion/complexity analysis. In this regard, this section will discuss the selected software implementations, the choice of coding parameters, and the corresponding evaluation setup.

3.1 Encoder Implementations and Codec Configurations

In this subsection, we provide detailed codec configurations for the most recent available encoder implementations of the two video coding technologies under study, namely VVC and AV1, and for the anchor standard, HEVC.

With respect to HEVC, the HM reference software encoder was selected as the main HEVC representative [9]. It should be noted that this reference software is considered to be the most popular HEVC-based implementation for evaluating the coding efficiency of all HEVC-conforming coding tools, in spite of the existence of other HEVC-compliant encoders that provide a better trade-off between encoding speed and coding efficiency [20]. For conducting the corresponding HEVC performance evaluation, we selected HM version 16.16, whose configuration can be easily adjusted to the corresponding common test conditions (CTC) and configuration recommended by the JVET [21]. This document specifies, among other things, the sequences used to compare different proposals and their characteristics, and the GOP length.

The VTM encoder was selected for evaluating VVC, which comprises a collection of future video coding tools implemented on top of HEVC [22]. Particularly, the authors used VTM version 2.0.1.

For evaluating the AV1 encoder, the authors selected its latest release at the moment of writing, which is version 1.0 errata 1, that was made available in April 2019 [23]. It should be noted that parallel processing in AV1 strictly relies on the usage of tiles, thereby involving coding efficiency penalties. As a consequence, multithreading in AV1 was disabled in the experiments to avoid

Table 1 Encoder parameters used for evaluation.

Encoder	Parameters
HM 16.16	<pre>-c ../cfg/encoder_randomaccess_main10.cfg -c ../cfg/per-sequence/input_sequence.cfg -i input_sequence -b output_sequence -q qp -ip intra_period</pre>
VTM 2.0.1	<pre>-c ../cfg/encoder_randomaccess_vtm.cfg -c ../cfg/per-sequence/input_sequence.cfg -i input_sequence -b output_sequence -q qp -ip intra_period</pre>
AV1 1.0 e1	<pre>input_sequence -o output_sequence --codec=av1 --cpu-used=preset --i420 -w width -h height -b 10 --fps=frames_per_second/1 --good --tune=psnr --end-usage=q --passes=1 --min-gf-interval=16 --max-gf-interval=16 --min-q=minimum_qp --max-q=maximum_qp --psnr --kf-min-dist=intra_period --kf-max-dist=intra_period --threads=1 --verbose</pre>

adverse effects in its coding efficiency. The HM and VTM implementations are both single-threaded.

As mentioned in Subsection 2.3, AV1 features fine control over the trade-off between encoding speed and compression efficiency by the use of so-called presets, which control different encoding options such as partitioning depth or prediction modes used. These presets range from the slowest one (preset 0), which provides the highest quality possible at the expense of significant encoding times, to the fastest (preset 8), which prioritizes speed over visual quality. With the aim of evaluating the influence of such presets on the encoding, and to ensure a more equitable comparison, multiple presets were evaluated. The HM and VTM encoders, in turn, do not include predefined presets.

The HM and VTM encoders are typically tested by using static QP values, in particular 22, 27, 32 and 37, according to the CTCs. The AV1 encoder, however, can be evaluated by using two different approaches on the basis of the rate-control algorithms detailed in Subsection 2.3. On the one hand, it can be evaluated on the basis of static QP configurations that match the above HM and VTM CTCs and their corresponding target bitrates, and on the other hand, it can be tested using its built-in multi-pass rate-control mechanism. To make the evaluation comparable with existing analyses, we opted for the first of the listed alternatives. In this regard, given that it is necessary to specify a range of QP values for AV1, the QP ranges used for this encoder were 27–35, 35–43, 46–54 and 55–63 with the aim of ensuring its comparability with QP values 22, 27, 32 and 37 of HM and VTM [12]. The specific parameters used for each encoder to ensure a fair comparison are listed in Table 1.

The hardware platform used in the experiments is composed of an Intel® Xeon® E5-2630L v3 CPU running at 1.80 GHz and 16 GB of main memory. The encoders have been compiled with GCC 4.8.5-4 and executed on CentOS 7 (Linux 3.10.0-327). Turbo Boost has been disabled to achieve the reproducibility of the results.

3.2 Sequences

To ensure a common framework for the simulations, the experiments were conducted under the CTC recommended by the JVET for the RA mode configuration [21]. This recommendation specifies the use of 28 test sequences classified in seven classes, namely A1, A2, B, C, D, E and F, which cover a wide range of resolutions from the largest (3840×2160 pixels) to the smallest (416×240 pixels), and frame rates from 20 to 100 frames per second. Input bit depths are 8 and 10-bit, although the encodings were performed using 10-bit depth. All the sequences use 4:2:0 chroma subsampling. The sequences evaluated are:

- Class A1 (3840×2160 pixels): Tango2, Drums100, Campfire, and Toddler-Fountain2.
- Class A2 (3840×2160 pixels): CatRobot, TrafficFlow, DaylightRoad2, and Rollercoaster2.
- Class B (1920×1800 pixels): Kimono, ParkScene, Cactus, BQTerrace, and BasketballDrive.
- Class C (832×480 pixels): RaceHorsesC, BQMall, PartyScene, and BasketballDrill.
- Class D (416×240 pixels): RaceHorses, BQSquare, BlowingBubbles, and BasketballPass.
- Class E (1280×720 pixels): FourPeople, Johnny, and KristenAndSara.
- Class F (832×480 , 1024×768 , and 1280×720 pixels): BasketballDrillText, ChinaSpeed, SlideEditing, and SlideShow.

Figure 5 shows a distribution of the sequences according to their spatial and temporal indices, which indicate the complexity of the sequence through the information contained in each frame and between frames [24]. This figure demonstrates the variety of content available in the CTC video sequences, with different characteristics and features.

3.3 Metrics

The rate-distortion/complexity analysis was evaluated in terms of encoder run time (ERT) factor and R-D performance. The ERT factor was computed following Eq. 1, where $\text{Enc. Time}_{\text{test}}$ and $\text{Enc. Time}_{\text{reference}}$ represent the encoding times of the evaluated encoder and the baseline encoder, respectively.

$$\text{ERT} = \frac{\text{Enc. Time}_{\text{test}}}{\text{Enc. Time}_{\text{reference}}} \quad (1)$$

Regarding the R-D performance, the average PSNR metric was calculated for each luma (PSNR_Y) and chroma components (PSNR_U , PSNR_V) and for the full number of frames of each sequence. In order to obtain a global quality measure, the average PSNR of the three components, denoted as PSNR_{YUV} , was also computed. As mentioned above, the chroma subsampling format of

Fig. 5 SI and TI of the test sequences. Classes: A (Red), B (Yellow), C (Green), D (Black), E (Purple) and F (Blue).

the test sequences was 4:2:0, so the well-known PSNR_{YUV} according to Eq. 2 was used, which applies weight pondering to the PSNR obtained for each component. Those weights are recommended by the JCT-VC and they are considered a fair representation of the visual quality, which is more sensitive to the luminance stimulus than the chrominance [25].

$$\text{PSNR}_{YUV} = \frac{6 \cdot \text{PSNR}_Y + \text{PSNR}_U + \text{PSNR}_V}{8} \quad (2)$$

The PSNR_{YUV} for the four QPs were used for the computation of the R-D performance by using the BD-rate metric defined by ITU-T and recommended by the JCT-VC [16, 17]. This metric provides the average difference between the R-D curves measured as a percentage of bit rate that is necessary to increase or decrease to achieve the same PSNR quality in both curves. In our simulation, a positive BD-rate means the encoded bit rate using the test codec under study is higher than the bit rate obtained with the reference codec, thus that is denoted as the penalty in terms of bit rate.

4 Rate-Distortion/Complexity Analysis

In this section, we compare the coding efficiency and complexity of the three codecs. All codecs operated single-threaded to allow a fair comparison. As mentioned in the previous section, VTM and HM can be easily adjusted to the CTCs while the configuration options in AV1 have been studied to obtain similar behavior. However, AV1 implements a system of presets that vary from the slowest configuration (preset 0), which provides the best possible coding efficiency, to the fastest configuration (preset 8), where compression is sacrificed

Table 2 Encoder run time (ERT) factors and coding efficiency (BD-rate) of AV1 presets using preset 0 as anchor.

Class	Sequence	AV1 Preset 2		AV1 Preset 4		AV1 Preset 8	
		ERT	BD-rate (%)	ERT	BD-rate (%)	ERT	BD-rate (%)
A1	Tango2	0.33	3.98	0.13	7.84	0.07	19.90
	Drums100	0.28	6.95	0.12	9.44	0.06	22.34
	Campfire	0.34	3.60	0.17	9.40	0.11	21.98
	ToddlerFountain2	0.24	2.52	0.14	5.42	0.07	9.66
A2	CatRobot	0.33	5.51	0.12	8.80	0.07	24.12
	TrafficFlow	0.30	2.10	0.11	6.20	0.06	23.26
	DaylightRoad2	0.30	5.10	0.12	9.15	0.06	23.69
	RollerCoaster2	0.36	9.12	0.13	17.72	0.08	36.22
B	Kimono	0.32	2.91	0.13	5.47	0.07	13.45
	ParkScene	0.30	2.78	0.13	6.61	0.07	18.70
	Cactus	0.34	4.94	0.11	9.36	0.06	23.42
	BasketballDrive	0.30	5.11	0.12	10.47	0.07	26.18
	BQTerrace	0.27	5.53	0.11	10.77	0.06	44.32
C	BasketballDrill	0.30	5.13	0.14	9.15	0.07	19.70
	BQMall	0.29	5.13	0.13	9.58	0.07	25.76
	PartyScene	0.28	4.63	0.13	8.23	0.07	26.30
	RaceHorsesC	0.33	4.25	0.15	7.98	0.08	23.54
D	BasketballPass	0.30	3.68	0.14	7.75	0.07	17.72
	BQSquare	0.25	3.48	0.13	9.50	0.07	46.12
	BlowingBubbles	0.27	2.94	0.14	7.17	0.07	25.11
	RaceHorses	0.32	3.44	0.16	6.37	0.08	18.24
E	FourPeople	0.27	2.33	0.11	7.47	0.06	19.48
	Johnny	0.28	3.03	0.10	9.37	0.07	32.04
	KristenAndSara	0.29	2.64	0.11	7.89	0.07	25.03
F	BasketballDrillText	0.30	5.97	0.14	10.02	0.07	24.18
	ChinaSpeed	0.32	5.93	0.14	10.66	0.08	19.83
	SlideEditing	0.29	5.24	0.11	14.17	0.08	25.65
	SlideShow	0.45	6.23	0.23	13.05	0.17	38.18
Average (all sequences)		0.29	4.44	0.12	9.11	0.07	24.79

to reduce computational complexity. For this reason, we first analyzed the impact of these presets on the coding performance of the AV1 codec by selecting presets 0, 2, 4 and 8 as representatives of different coding configurations.

Table 2 shows the ERT factor and coding efficiency of AV1 presets 2, 4 and 8 over preset 0. It can be seen that when faster presets are enabled, the encoder takes shortcuts to improve performance at the expense of quality and compression efficiency. When the slowest preset is used, AV1 uses more complex encoding tools that achieve better visual quality. The results show that presets 4 and 8 introduce large penalties in terms of BD-rate, while preset 2 achieves a large reduction in computational complexity compared to the placebo version of the encoder with a small penalty of 4.44% BD-rate. Therefore, preset 2 has been taken as the reference preset for the AV1 codec in the analysis against HM and VTM.

Table 3 Encoder run time (ERT) factors and coding efficiency (BD-rate) results of HM, VTM and AV1.

Class	Sequence	VTM (HM anchor)		AV1 (HM anchor)		VTM (AV1 anchor)	
		ERT	BD-rate (%)	ERT	BD-rate (%)	ERT	BD-rate (%)
A1	Tango2	3.61	-32.24	0.88	14.72	3.87	-39.55
	Drums100	3.40	-26.85	1.11	36.03	2.98	-45.37
	Campfire	6.03	-27.62	1.36	-8.53	4.33	-20.54
	ToddlerFountain2	7.16	-13.58	1.18	-5.56	5.98	-8.14
A2	CatRobot	3.35	-34.62	1.36	33.56	2.37	-50.49
	TrafficFlow	2.55	-24.21	1.31	58.90	1.82	-53.35
	DaylightRoad2	4.08	-32.70	1.37	46.41	2.80	-53.53
	RollerCoaster2	2.60	-33.67	0.73	23.32	3.43	-45.53
B	Kimono	3.55	-17.94	1.22	46.49	2.81	-44.08
	ParkScene	3.22	-16.57	1.96	70.13	1.61	-51.31
	Cactus	3.96	-27.85	2.03	55.80	1.91	-53.66
	BasketballDrive	4.44	-27.62	1.19	23.88	3.64	-40.90
	BQTerrace	2.76	-25.91	1.93	54.56	1.39	-51.22
C	BasketballDrill	4.30	-21.67	1.41	49.72	3.03	-48.23
	BQMall	3.47	-21.17	1.34	54.42	2.57	-48.72
	PartyScene	3.93	-20.12	2.32	73.11	1.69	-53.53
	RaceHorsesC	4.67	-17.32	1.38	20.64	3.35	-31.27
D	BasketballPass	4.76	-18.15	1.43	28.33	3.30	-36.09
	BQSquare	2.75	-23.40	2.05	90.36	1.33	-59.85
	BlowingBubbles	3.90	-16.98	2.44	74.39	1.59	-52.14
	RaceHorses	4.75	-16.04	1.61	27.71	2.94	-34.26
E	FourPeople	2.03	-23.70	1.00	63.23	1.97	-53.25
	Johnny	1.53	-25.79	0.94	58.96	1.54	-53.46
	KristenAndSara	1.94	-24.16	0.91	68.84	2.03	-55.61
F	BasketballDrillText	4.13	-21.87	1.42	49.92	2.89	-48.37
	ChinaSpeed	3.39	-18.47	0.98	24.94	3.45	-34.71
	SlideEditing	1.18	-13.39	0.68	-8.17	1.74	-5.11
	SlideShow	1.50	-26.58	0.47	25.65	3.15	-43.39
Average (all sequences)		4.45	-23.22	1.28	41.15	3.49	-43.42

Having selected a reference preset for AV1, Table 3 shows the experimental results of HM, VTM and AV1 video codecs under study for the RA configuration. The two first columns represent the results of both VTM and AV1 codecs when considering HM as baseline encoder, and the third column displays the results of VTM when using AV1 preset 2 as baseline encoder.

In terms of coding efficiency, it can be observed that VTM outperforms both HM and AV1 codecs with 23.22% and 43.42% BD-rate gains on average, respectively. These gains are fairly homogeneous across classes when comparing VTM and HM, while there are some outliers in the case of AV1. These outliers correspond to sequences that are characterized by unusual content such as dozens of flows of water, and slideshow presentations. When comparing AV1 against HM, however, it turns out that the former is not able to outperform the latter in terms of BD-rate in most cases.

Fig. 6 R-D curves of HM, VTM and AV1 (preset 2) for all sequences.

Table 3 also compares the ERT factors normalized to the corresponding reference codec. In terms of complexity, both ongoing developments, AV1 and VTM, require more encoding time to achieve the higher compression efficiency. It is observed that VTM increases the ERT significantly compared to HM, with a factor of $4.45\times$. AV1 also increases the encoding time, albeit with an ERT factor lower than VTM, i.e. $1.28\times$ compared to HM.

Fig. 7 Total encoding time of HM, VTM and AV1 (preset 2) for the four QP parameters and all sequences.

To analyze the coding efficiency of HM, VTM and AV1 preset 2 in further detail, Fig. 6 shows the R-D curves of the three encoders, enabling a better view of their compression performance. Higher PSNR and lower bitrate values represent better coding efficiency. Therefore, encoders whose curves are closer to the top-left corner of the plots imply greater efficiency. As can be seen, the R-D performance of VTM is greater than that of HM in all cases. In this

regard, it has to be taken into consideration that the former is an evolution of the latter. In the case of AV1, however, this encoder cannot outperform the performance provided by HM, with the exception of certain specific sequences due to the reasons discussed above. The total encoding time of the encoders, in turn, is depicted in Fig. 7 for the four QP values used in the experiments. This figure shows that the encoding time required by VTM exceeds that of HM or AV1 significantly. Similarly, AV1 generally requires larger encoding times than HM in spite of not delivering equivalent coding efficiency.

In view of the results, it could be concluded that both ongoing developments, VVC and the AV1 project, differ in many aspects on the basis of their main encoders. While the aim of the two encoders is to become the new leader in video coding, VTM has proven to achieve significantly greater coding efficiency than current generation encoders and AV1. However, its computational complexity has also proven to be significantly high, which may hinder the implementation of this standard in the short term. Even though AV1 tries to address this problem by targeting current technology as main receptor of its advances in video coding, the above experimental evaluation has shown that this encoder is not able to outperform HM. Therefore, it still needs to progress in the development of new encoding tools.

5 Conclusions

This paper presents a rate-distortion/complexity analysis of the HEVC, VVC and AV1 video codecs using objective measures of assessment in order to analyze their real capabilities. For this purpose, we analyzed the distinguishing features of the new codecs in comparison with HEVC. The results show the current development status and indicate a tendency regarding achievable coding-efficiency improvements, on the one hand, and necessary computing costs in terms of encoding time, on the other hand. Our main findings are that VTM, the main VVC-compliant encoder in the state of the art, considerably outperforms HM and AV1 in terms of coding efficiency while AV1 cannot transform increased complexity into better coding efficiency compared to VTM or HM.

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